

WHAT ARE THE BEST AND MOST EFFECTIVE METHODS USED IN NOTE-TAKING PROCESS DURING LECTURES?

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Abstract: This thesis aims to define several techniques which can be relevant for students while making notes during lectures. It is essential to think deeply about providing various methods and techniques for students as the vast majority of them struggle with choosing an appropriate format or do not even aware of applying them properly. Several workable methods which are suggested by different authors will be discussed below

Key words and phrases: linear note-taking style, non-linear note-taking style, iconic signs, a solid comprehension, abbreviation, long-lasting retention, Sentence method, syntax transformation

The thesis aims to define several techniques which can be suitable for students while making notes. The vast majority of students struggle with choosing an appropriate format and do not aware of using them properly. We should consider that "cannot be equated to simply copying what is heard, observed or thought" (Piolat, 2004, p. 291). It is obvious that even though various ways are available, not all of them can be relevant for learners. The most effective ones assist not only to perceive the information in a deeper sense, but also to review them before exams or while they are forgotten to save time efficiently. As Kiewra (1989) pointed out that responding to this question is a complex aspect, since each student has different learning preferences, and picking one particular depends mainly on them. Note taking process could even fail or become incomplete without using well-organized methods. As a result of the aforementioned reasons, I decided to review and come up with the most beneficial and advantageous methods by comparing and analyzing scholars' attitudes toward mentioned topic. This review covers introduction, main body, and conclusion, in addition, a reference list with citations will be provided at the end.

Note-taking is divided into two main categories: linear and non-linear. According to Piolat (2001), linear is considered as the same as the written text. Most students found it handy during lectures since they should be able to keep a record while the essential information will be conveyed by the lecturer to the audience.

Both listening and writing skills are required at the same time. Thus, learners tend to choose this method to make the process effortless. Conversely, the non-linear style is challenging for students to perceive, it covers graphic representations, charts, tables, and diagrams. This method is known as an uncommon style for the vast majority of students, due to the fact that they might skip supplied data during lectures by being engaged in drawing and making graphics. However, Piolat (2001) rejected this by noting that the non-linear method is more helpful and assists to ease the process by making synthesis. Other scholars Makany, Kemp, & Dror (2008), and Rahmani & Sadeghi (2011) also supported Piolat's approach, taking graphic organizers into consideration is one of the most workable techniques for students while participating in lectures, owing to the reason of saving time efficiently. This technique also gives a chance to dive deeply into the note-taking process and to make a solid comprehension Dijk & Kintsch (1983) mention that in most cases comprehension is an indispensable and pivotal part of taking notes. Robin et al (1977) added that note-takers may not only enlarge the perfection of context, but also enhance educational outcomes. A great number of university resources recommend using Cornell Notes. Boye (2012) states this method teaches to organize and group the data, practice acquired knowledge in various ways which put forward recalling the topic for a longer period of time. Another advantage of Cornell Notes is that it can be relevant for both linear and non-linear styles. It composes of 3 stages, particularly the right side for formal notes which might be taken directly during listening lectures, the left column can be used for making questions and highlighting keywords regarding the right, and lastly, the bottom includes the writer's personal brief opinions in terms of the discussed topic and provides understanding it at the level of perfection. Interestingly, most learners already remember, and absorbed the main core of the topic and can express their ideas in summary without making a strong effort. Boye (2012) and Piolat (2004) emphasized using the abbreviation technique by shortening words and pointing symbols during lectures. Their attitudes overlap in many cases, the types of abbreviations are varied both among the majority of students and even within one particular learner. It means, students may use one abbreviation for the supplied word while listening to lectures, and then another completely different one will be put to use for the same word again.

The following key technique of syntax transformation has also been found favorable

for students. They shorten statements by adding iconic signs. This technique aids in recognizing information visually and identifying the links between sentences as most learners opt for a visual learning style.

Boye (2012) discusses that leaving empty spaces is proposed and advised, so that students might be able to accomplish them after lectures or complete up to the end if they were hesitant while taking notes. Additionally, Potts (1993) supported Boye's points, the lecturer might likely revise the aforementioned details once more, or students themselves can summarize in total the main gist and end up with them.

The method of selective attention facilitates adequately the process of making notes. Note-takers might draw their attention to the notes on the blackboard, the lecturer's repetition, pauses, changes in the tone of voice, gestures, highlighted and strongly emphasized key terms and terminologies, definitions, and main questions (Boye, 2012). Moreover, Lutman (2001) concludes, learners must strongly pay attention to the phrases that characterize the introductory and concluding parts, such as "This is an important point", "In conclusion", "To sum things up" as well as to linking words which structure the topic. The technique of reviewing notes is also well-chosen to make solidified notes. DeZure et al (2001) claim that peer reviewing after lectures can serve as an assistance for correcting unclear information, completing skipped notes, and considering them thoroughly after lectures. Boye (2012) backed up his points, the most dominant and superior technique is sharing notes with someone.

Note-taking would not be regarded as fully achieved after lectures, it should be recalled occasionally to save long-lasting retention. Furthermore, working individually is also taking a positive aspect, by using it learners may reorganize their notes in an alternative way. Oppositely, King (1992) denied that observing the concluding part and taking final questions into account has a more beneficial impact on students' memorization.

Instructors should familiarize plainly their students with various techniques and allow them to assess, practice, and select the most worked and affordable one since everyone has own preferences and learning styles. In addition, inspiring learners to generate untouched systems for themselves. Even though the learner was not able to become aware of the mentioned information, he or she could make a record of it directly on time while it was conveyed to get to know and determine more closely after lectures. Without clarifying them, learners may struggle with catching the fundamental point. Another leading aspect that learners should decide carefully is using a laptop or papers for discussed above

techniques. Laptops might be distractive for note-takers and the vast majority of learners are not able to type faster than writing by pen. The speed of making notes is substantially crucial for students during lectures and preparation for it also stands as an indispensable part before lectures.

When information is difficult to perceive, it is better to use the Sentence Method. Here, students may directly write in a sentence the shared data while the lecture is being conducted and simply start with new lines, in case unstated ideas or facts are mentioned. It is paramount to revise them after the lecture or rewrite the same notes once again by focusing on organization and including some other alternatives to make them more comprehensible. One more thing that is important to accentuate, numerous students try to write down all mentioned lecturer's points which can lead to later confusion. To achieve effective note-taking results, learners should skip unnecessary data to avoid overloading. There is no doubt that the human brain receives only short-lasting information.

To sum up, Note-taking methods are varied and this review discussed the most workable ones, there is no one particular which can be suitable for learners. Each of them has both benefits and drawbacks. Students should come up with a method that overlaps their learning styles and preferences. If they study different subjects, they may pick more methods for using during lectures. Cornelius & Owen-DeSchryver (2008) remarked that at first, teachers and instructors have to acquaint students with methods and then should provide an opportunity for practicing broadly them, limiting with just explanation is inadequate. "It is necessary to overview the main techniques that can be used to exploit note-taking to its full potential, and to facilitate it" (Piolat, 2004, p. 291). Putting scholars' approaches together has been noticed that most analyzed ideas coincide with one another. Scholars could not come to one single decision while analyzing the best optimal methods as long as the question itself is investigated as arduous and intricate. They concluded that students will identify themselves with the most applicable methods and techniques in the time of practicing them.

References:

1. Boye, A. (2012). Note-taking in the 21st century: Tips for instructors and students. Retrieved July 16, 2015, from
2. https://www.depts.ttu.edu/tlpdc/Resources/Teaching_resources/TLPDC_teaching_resources/Documents/NotetakingWhitepaper.pdf
3. Kiewra, K. A. (1989). A more equitable account of the note-taking functions in learning from lecture and from text. *Instructional Science*, 18, 217–

4. King, A. (1992) Comparison of self-questioning, summarizing, and notetaking review as strategies for learning from lectures. *American Educational Research Journal*, 29. (2), 303-323
5. Lutman, J. (2001). *Student Guide to Effective Notetaking and Review*. Center for Research on Learning and Teaching (CRLT)
6. Makany, T., Kemp, J. & Dror, I.E. (2008). Optimizing the use of note-taking as an external cognitive aid for increasing learning. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 10, 1 - 17
7. Piolat, A. (2001). Cognitive effort of note taking. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 18, 1-22.
8. Piolat, A. (2004). What are the most optimal methods of note-taking? Retrieved June 23, 1988, from
9. http://www.academia.edu/39178549/Note_taking_Instruction_Its_Impact_on_Information
10. Potts, B. (1993). Improving the quality of student notes. Retrieved July 29, 2015, from <http://pareonline.net/getvn.asp?v=3&n=8>
11. Rahmani, M. & Sadeghi, K. (2011). Effects of Note-Taking Training on
12. Comprehension and Recall. *An International Online Journal*, 11 (2), 116-128
13. Robin, A., Foxx, R. M., Martello, J., & Archable, C. (1977). Teaching note: Taking skills to underachieving college students. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 71, 81-85. doi:10.2307/27537081

